

LLM-powered Assistants for Advanced Geospatial Dataset Recommendations based on Geolocated Queries

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Integrating Earth observation, meteorological, and sensor data into domain-specific research often requires substantial pre-existing knowledge. Leveraging Large Language Models (LLMs) to interpret natural language prompts offers a solution, enabling scientists in fields such as climate science, biology, humanities, and economics to access relevant geospatial datasets intuitively. This paper presents an innovative system using LLMs, specifically through Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG), to recommend advanced geospatial datasets based on geolocated queries. Developed using the LangChain framework, the system incorporates data from sources like Destination Earth, Eurostat, and ECMWF, dynamically expanding its knowledge base with online data. This approach provides precise dataset recommendations and bibliographic references, enhancing research integration and application. The architecture, workflow, and technical implementation are detailed, emphasizing the system's traceability, multi-LLM integration, and effectiveness, as demonstrated through improved answer relevance and relevant data collection recommendations.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context

1.1.1 Context of use

Scientists specializing in climate, biology, humanities, or economics would benefit from integrating Earth observation data, meteorological data, and sensor data into their research. However, current portals holding such data require pre-existing knowledge of the data and their use. With the development of Large Language Models (LLMs) to interpret natural language prompts into specific domains, this barrier to entry could be significantly reduced or removed.

Currently, the use of LLMs is often limited to generating textual or media responses [1]. However, for the targeted user, the main added value lies in providing pointers to data collections and products from Earth observation, meteorology, climatology, national statistics, on-site sensors, biosphere extents, etc., as

well as references to adjacent published research. Providing those information on top of a textual answer bootstraps the integration of such products into the targeted domain-specific research or applications. In this paper, we are describing an innovative system providing such information relying heavily on LLMs. The presented system is licensed under Apache 2.0 Open Source Licence.

1.1.2 Data Leveraged

The proposed system currently focuses on providing Earth observation data (imagery, altimetry, radar) from satellite-embedded sensors, combined with meteorological forecasts, climatology analyses and models, national and local statistics (population ages, genders), and ground sensors (hydrology/meteorology stations).

The system leverages data from Destination Earth [2], including Earth observation data from ESA, EUMETSAT, and NASA; national statistics from Eurostat [3]; and meteorological and climatology forecasts and analysis from ECMWF [4], other earth observation data are retrieved from THEIA [5]. The system also incorporates other data sources to build a domain-specific knowledge base, integrating articles from Wikipedia, published articles referenced in Google Scholar, YouTube videos and Listen Notes podcasts such as the "Watching Our Earth" series from EUMETSAT [6], and the ESA Data Ontology [7].

1.1.3 Technical Context

LLMs are powerful tools that have significantly improved their outputs' quality and level of generalisation over the past few years, allowing end users to interact with complex systems of knowledge in an intuitive way using natural language. However, the outputs of these powerful LLMs tend to lack specificity, and references to datasets used in their training [8]. Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) integrates these LLMs with specific knowledge databases

Figure 1: Architecture of the system

Figure 2: User Mode interface

to reduce those limitations. The use of RAG also enables a continuous and dynamic expansion of the knowledge base, while complex LLMs are fixed and limited to the state of their training dataset. [9].

LLMs used in RAG can be remotely accessed (e.g., ChatGPT, Gemini, Llama) or deployed on dedicated instances (Llama, Mistral, Dolphin), the proposed system has been demonstrated, integrated with gpt-3.5-turbo and a local instance of Llama 3 for example. Local instances can also be fine-tuned to a specific context and is the intent of future experimentations.

The proposed system is using the framework LangChain (including LangServe and LangSmith) to define complex processing chains [10], to integrate LLMs, data sources, RAG, vector databases, complex behaviors of the system. To enable a user-friendly in-

terface for our end users, we used the open-software solution (OSS) REACT framework TOPAZ to develop the web-based graphical interface.

1.2 Details of Research

1.2.1 Architecture

The proposed system includes processing steps to integrate the various datasets into a vector database, both at rest and dynamically, as well as the main workflow described in 1 to react to a new user prompt.

The system is based on Langchain, a framework that relies on the concept of chains to describe Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) pipelines made for generative AI workflows. Including connecting objects or func-

tions such as LLMs, retrievers, tools and preprocessing steps [11]. The architecture of our pipeline relies on them to perform the processing and interpretation of the user’s query.

To explain the behavior of the main workflow 1 and the interaction between the system and the user through the user interface 2, we will detail an example of a prompt provided by a societal researcher studying the impact of high-speed rail on local populations. The user enters in (Fig2-1) the prompt field: "How has the construction of new high-speed rail lines in the capital of Spain from 2015 to 2024 affected population migration patterns and urban sprawl in the surrounding metropolitan area, as evidenced by geospatial data analysis?" which is displayed in (Fig2-2).

The query is parsed with the LLM in order to retrieve spatio-temporal data (Fig1-A).

The LLM will detect the type of landmark (city, mountain chain, river, lake, etc...) and put it in the correct format to query Nominatim [12], which will return the Geojson of the corresponding region. In (Fig3) there are example of GeoJSONs generated tailored to the Pyrenees Mountain Range, the Garonne River and the city of Biarritz (city near the Spain-France frontier, just above the Pyrenees).

Figure 3: Example of GeoJSON produced

(Fig2-6). The time-frame is also extracted and normalised by the LLM. From the previous query "the capital of Spain" is interpreted as "Madrid", and a GeoJSON file is retrieved from Madrid’s geographical coordinates. "2015 to 2024" is normalised to "2015-01-01T00:00:00z/2024-12-31T23:59:59Z".

The relevant context is retrieved from a vector database [13](Fig1-B) by applying similarity search with the input prompt, allowing to retrieve references from the database and from the list of available data collections. Those information are provided to the LLM (Fig1-C) to produce a textual answer. (Fig2-3).

The LLM is questioned to extract adjacent topics (Fig1-D) and retrieve additional knowledge from on-line sources (Wikipedia [14], Articles referenced by

Google Scholar) that are then dynamically added to the Vector Database. For instance "High-speed rail lines", "Population migration patterns" and "Urban sprawl" were extracted from the prompt, then documents about high speed rails from other regions of the world were retrieved. Once the generalized query generated "How has the development of high-speed rail networks in Europe influenced population migration patterns and urban sprawl in surrounding metropolitan areas ?", allows to provide examples of similar analysis on other European cities in the bibliography.

The steps (Fig1-B) and (Fig1-C) are then repeated based on this expanded knowledge (Fig1-B2) and (Fig1-C2). This new answer is provided in (Fig2-4). While the second answer (Fig2-4) is more complete and specific, the first answer (Fig2-3) is already of a good quality and provided to improve the reactivity of the system, allowing to reword the prompt if a significant misunderstanding is noticed by the user.

Earth observation products, climatology analysis, and more, identified as relevant to the prompt are provided to the user (Fig2-7) and displayed on the map (Fig2-5). Here CAMS, CLMS, Sentinel 1 and Eurostat data are retrieved from Destination Earth [15] using the Open Source library EODAG [16] (Fig1-E). The Bibliography is also provided after being formatted by the LLM (Fig2-8).

1.2.2 Traceability

Despite the black-box issue that comes from the use of large scale LLMs [8], the proposed system is tailored to keep track and monitor the entirety of the process, recording both the input, the output and the behavior of each processing steps. References from all documents used in the process are retained and made clearly accessible to the user. It gives access to the user to an in depth look at what were the inputs and output at any given moments of the processing. The additional traceability mechanisms are integrated into Langsmith [10]. The explanations allows the researchers to redirect the research to specific papers and datasets according to the use case.

1.2.3 Multi LLM integration

The proposed system has been tested leveraging a remote LLM, gpt-3.5-turbo, gpt-4 as well as using a LLM deployed locally with Llama 3. The answer provided with both system were, as expected [17], of similar quality but allow to either optimize the cost or the data privacy of the system [18].

Figure 4: Developer Mode Interface

2 Results

2.1 Corpus of documents

The initial corpus of document ingested into the vector database included the definition of 94 of the datasets provided by Destination Earth [15], the entire ESA Data Ontology [7], around 2000 Wikipedia articles related to Earth Observation, climatology and weather forecast, a dozen of videos and podcasts from the EUMETSAT's "Watching Our Earth" series [6]. While the ontology and the Wikipedia's articles are only used to provide specificity to the textual answers (Fig2-3) and (Fig2-4), the other data are also used to provide suggested datasets (Fig2-7) and products.

During the step (Fig1-D), additional articles from Wikipedia and articles referenced from Google Scholar have been ingested and embedded into the vector database. The current configuration adds around 15 articles from Wikipedia and up to 15 from Google Scholar (including full article content when available through journal's subscription).

2.2 Metrics and LLM comparison

To gauge the effectiveness of our proposed solution by using popular benchmarks we created a dataset of 11 hydrology related questions. Responses to these questions were generated by gpt-3.5-turbo alone to compare to the proposed system leveraging gpt-3.5-turbo. We used RAGAS metric **Answer Relevancy**. It showed marginal differences : gpt-3.5-turbo scored **0.929** ($\sigma = 0.036$), slightly lower than the system's response at **0.948** ($\sigma = 0.034$).

2.3 Methodology for the human assessment

As the added value of the system is not only the textual answer but also the dataset suggestion and provided bibliography, we inquired the judgment of expert (PhD), and knowledgeable (research engineers) from CS to assess the outputs of the tool (7 in total). A set of 5 hydrology-based prompts was created. The prompt pool was limited to 5 to avoid overwhelming the respondents. For each prompt the assessor had to grade :

- Textual answer from ChatGPT-3.5
- Textual answer from the tool
- Expanded Textual answer from the tool
- Bibliography suggested
- Dataset suggested

The assessor is asked for each of those items to grade the relevancy and quality of the provided answer based on their knowledge as well as their own research using search engines and documentation specific to hydrology use cases. Each grade is an integer between 0 and 10.

Here is an example of a prompt : *" I want to study the evolution of the net hydrological balance of the Rhine basin in France in the 2010's "*

with the corresponding answer from the tool: *To study the evolution of the net hydrological balance of the Rhine basin in France during the 2010s, you can refer to datasets that provide information on river discharge and hydrological variables. The dataset you might find useful*

is the one that provides a gridded modelled time series of river discharge forced with seasonal range meteorological reforecasts. This dataset is a product of the Global Flood Awareness System (GloFAS) and is produced by forcing a hydrological modelling chain with input from the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) ensemble seasonal forecasting system, SEAS5. It covers the period from 1981 to 2016 with 25 ensemble members and from 2017 onwards with a 51-member ensemble. This dataset can help you assess the evolution of the net hydrological balance by providing seasonal river discharge thresholds and a long time period for analysis. Additionally, you may want to look into the European Flood Awareness System (EFAS) forecasts and historical simulations specifically for European hydrological data. These datasets are part of operational flood forecasting within the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) and can provide valuable information for your study.

The results obtained are as follows :

- The average score for the quality of the answer produced by ChatGPT is **5.85** ($\sigma = 0.12$), less than the average for the first answer produced by our system at **6.29** ($\sigma = 0.40$).
- The relevancy of ChatGPT only scored **5.57** ($\sigma = 0.13$) whereas our system is graded better on average for the system’s first answer at **6.50** ($\sigma = 0.55$).

Figure 5: Relevancy scores for each prompt

The 4th prompt lead the system to produce this answer :

" I'm sorry, but there is no specific information available regarding the water quality of Lake Pareloup between 2015 and 2020 in the provided context. The information provided mainly focuses on water quality monitoring in different areas and rivers, such as Lake Buyo and the Rhine River."

Instead of producing a general answer like ChatGPT does when it does not know how to answer and

with high probability of hallucination or misinformation, the system developed identified that it did not possess enough knowledge to produce an answer and clearly stated it.

3 Discussion

3.1 LLM and Human-based metrics

While RAGAS (Retrieval Augmented Generation Assessment) is a popular metric, it necessitates the use of an LLM in-the-loop, introducing inherent bias into the evaluation process [19]. To improve the metrics’ relevancy, additional corpus of input prompt have to be generated. The RAGAS metric should also be completed by metrics measuring the relevance of the collections and products suggested by the system. To provide human evaluation, the system integrates a multi-source answer-visualisation 4 linked with a voting mechanism to obtain feedback from experts. This tooling allows comparison of the system leveraging different LLMs or with external system (e.g. remote LLM without RAG).

3.2 New documents quality

The dynamic addition of documents from Google Scholar and Wikipedia adds a lot of value and relevance to the provided answer, however it does not allowed for quality checks. The degradation in the quality of article or false information would significantly negatively impact the system. Using metrics to estimate Wikipedia’s article quality or journal impact factor to discriminate articles could enhance the robustness of the system.

3.3 Advancements and Enhancements

Our upcoming focus lies in enhancing the quality of the generated responses. Various approaches can be pursued to achieve this goal. Firstly, exploring alternative LLMs involves effectively evaluating and comparing their behaviors on a dataset specific to our context [20]. Secondly, enhancing the retrieval process holds promise for improving response quality. Since the retriever plays a crucial role in providing the appropriate context to the LLM, advancements in similarity search can significantly impact response quality. Techniques such as modifying similarity metrics, thresholding, or reranking [21] have the potential to yield substantial improvements. Additionally, optimizing data chunk size could elevate the quality of retrieved context [22]. While reducing chunk size enhances precision, it requires increased memory for storage.

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